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CONTESTATIONEM PRO VERIBUS ET IUDICIO
MEO INTEGRE SERVATURUM ESSE...

APOLONOM LEKAROM I ESKULAPOM,
HIGIJOM I PANAKEJOM SE ZAKLINJEM I
POZIVAM ZA SVEDOKE SVE BOGOVE I
BOGINJE, DA ĆU OVU ZAKLETVU I OVO
PRIZIVANJE, PREMA SVOJIM MOĆIMA I
SVOM RASUĐIVANJU, U POTPUNOSTI
OČUVATI...

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STRUČNI RADovi

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PROCENA ZNANJA I STAVOVA ADOLESCENATA O REPRODUKTIVNOM ZDRAVLJU

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SAŽETAK

Uvod: Reproaktivno zdravlje predstavlja ključan segment ukupnog zdravlja adolescenata. Uprkos dostupnosti informacija, brojna istraživanja ukazuju na nedovoljno znanje mladih o ovoj temi.

Cilj: Procena znanja i stavova adolescenata o reproduktivnom zdravlju, kao i ispitivanje povezanost tih varijabli sa sociodemografskim faktorima.

Materijal i metode: Sprovedena studija uključivala je 958 učesnika, a podaci su prikupljeni pomoću anonimnog anketnog upitnika koji se sastojao iz tri grupe pitanja: demografske karakteristike, testa znanja i pitanja o sredstvima informisanja. Rezultati su analizirani deskriptivnim i inferencijalnim statističkim metodama.

Rezultati: Sprovedena studija brojala je 958 učenika. Prosečna starost svih ispitanih pri stupanju u prvi seksualni odnos bila je 16,4 godine. Muški ispitanici statistički značajno ranije stupaju u seksualne odnose. Viša prosečna starost pri prvom stupanju u seksualne odnose prisutna je kod većeg uspeha u školi. Po sopstvenoj proceni, većina ispitanika smatra da ima sve potrebne informacije o kontracepciji. Devojke su pokazale statistički značajno veće znanje i odgovorniji stav prema sopstvenom reproduktivnom zdravlju. Kontraceptivna sredstva koriste 87% onih koji su imali polne odnose. Sa problemom neželjene trudnoće susrelo se 1% ispitanih. Samo 42% ispitanika je posetilo ginekologa, urologa ili savetovalište za mlade. U najvećem broju slučajeva ispitanici se u slučaju problema mogu obratiti roditeljima (86%).

Zaključak: Rezultati ukazuju na potrebu za sistematskom sveobuhvatnom seksualnom edukacijom koja će biti prilagođena uzrastu. Neophodna je veća uključenost porodice, škole i zdravstvenih radnika u obrazovanje mladih o reproduktivnom zdravlju, radi podizanja nivoa znanja i osnaživanja adolescenata da donose informisane i odgovorne odluke.

Ključne reči: reproduktivno zdravlje, kontracepcija, adolescenti, seksualna edukacija

SUMMARY

Introduction: Reproductive health, a crucial component of adolescents' overall well-being, is a topic that continues to spark interest and concern. Despite the abundance of information available, a number of studies have pointed to a significant gap in young people's knowledge in this area.

Objective: to assess the knowledge and attitudes of adolescents about reproductive health, and to examine the connection of these variables with sociodemographic factors.

Materials and Methods: The study involved 958 participants. Data were collected through an anonymous survey questionnaire comprised of three groups of questions: demographic characteristics, a knowledge test, and questions regarding information sources. The results were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistical methods.

Results: The study revealed that the average age of all respondents at the time of their first sexual intercourse was 16.4 years. Male respondents statistically entered sexual relationships earlier. A higher average age at first sexual intercourse is linked to greater success in school. Most respondents believe they have all the necessary information about contraception. Girls demonstrated statistically significantly greater knowledge and a more responsible attitude toward their reproductive health. Contraceptives are used by 87% of those who have had sex. Only 1% of the respondents faced the issue of unwanted pregnancy. Only 42% of respondents visited a gynecologist, urologist, or youth counseling center. In most cases, respondents can turn to their parents in times of trouble. These findings shed light on the current state of adolescent reproductive health and can guide future interventions.

Conclusion: The results underscore the need for systematic, comprehensive sex education that is tailored to the age and needs of adolescents. This education should not only focus on the biological aspects of reproductive health but also on the social and emotional aspects. It is crucial to involve families, schools, and health workers in this education. Their active participation is necessary to ensure that young people are equipped with the knowledge and skills to make responsible decisions about their reproductive health.

Keywords: reproductive health, contraception, adolescents, sexual education.

Introduction

Adolescence is a period of rapid growth and sexual maturity that occurs between the ages of 10 and 19, marking the beginning of adulthood with numerous changes in a person's physical, psychological, emotional, and social well-being [1, 2]. During this period, adolescents can have serious health and social consequences. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), the most serious problems among adolescents are early pregnancy, childbirth, HIV, depression, the presence of violence, drug and alcohol abuse, intentional injuries, malnutrition, overweight, and tobacco use. These problems are increasingly recognized as serious global public health problems and are all associated with increased maternal mortality among pregnant adolescents and increased suicide rates among adolescent males [3]. One example is that a significant number of adolescents have some risky sexual behavior, and they do not receive appropriate treatment for the sexual health problems they face [4].

Reproductive health is a fundamental component of the general health and well-being of an individual, especially in the period of adolescence and early adulthood. According to the World Health Organization (WHO) definition, reproductive health refers to a state of complete physical, psychological, and social well-being in all aspects related to the reproductive system, encompassing not only the absence of disease or weakness but also the ability to have a satisfying and safe reproductive life. Preserving the reproductive health of young people is crucial for the prevention of unwanted pregnancies, sexually transmitted infections (STIs), as well as for building healthy attitudes towards sexuality, partnership, and responsibility [5].

Adolescent sexual and reproductive health is one of the most critical components of the global problem of PPI prevalence. Early sexual intercourse, often without adequate protection, increases the risk of numerous issues, from unwanted pregnancies to infections such as HPV, chlamydia, and HIV. At the same time, young people's attitudes towards contraception, abor-

tion, and sexual education are shaped under the strong influence of peers, media, family, and the educational system. These attitudes are often accompanied by risky habits that can have long-term consequences for reproductive and psychological health [6]. Today, international associations and agencies increasingly focus on improving sexual and reproductive health and provide numerous funding programs. In 2002, the Special Session of the United Nations General Assembly on Children acknowledged the need for the development and implementation of health policies and programs for adolescents to promote their physical and mental well-being [7].

The sexual and reproductive health of adolescents is strongly related to their social, cultural, and economic environment. In addition to regional variations, experiences vary by age, gender, education, residence, sexual orientation, and socioeconomic status [8, 9]. Access to healthcare and sources of education, information, and support also varies significantly across regions. These differences necessitate country-level research; however, despite these variations, key issues, barriers, and challenges, as well as potential solutions, can be identified at all levels [10].

Considering all of the above, it is necessary to systematically investigate the level of information among young people regarding reproductive health, as well as their attitudes and behaviors, to identify critical points and formulate guidelines for improving preventive programs and educational content.

Objective

The goal of this research is to provide insight into the current situation among young people, identify differences based on gender, age, and education, and highlight potential factors that shape their decisions and behaviors in the realm of sexual and reproductive health. Also, the goal is to examine the level of knowledge of young people about the fundamental aspects of reproductive health, as well as to analyze attitudes and habits related to sexual behavior.

Methods

For the research, a questionnaire consisting of three groups of questions was used. The first group of questions related to questions about basic demographic characteristics, the second group of questions (knowledge test) related to the questions associated to topics such as puberty, menstrual cycle, pregnancy, contraception and PPI, while the third group of questions included questions about who they would turn to for advice regarding problems in their sexual life, from whom they get the most information on this topic, as well as things related to communication with their partner when entering into sexual relations.

The data were collected anonymously and voluntarily between June 1, 2023, and June 1, 2025, with the consent of educational institutions. The aim of the research was explained to the participants, and participation was anonymous and voluntary, with no charge.

The research was conducted by the ethical principles for research involving minors, and all data were collected with full respect for the anonymity and confidentiality of the participants.

The data were processed using the software package SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences), version 21.0. Methods of descriptive statistics (average values, percentages, standard deviations) and inferential statistics were used - t-test for independent samples and Pearson's correlation, depending on the nature of the data and the goal of the analysis. Statistical significance was determined at the level of $p < 0.05$.

Results

A total of 958 adolescents, aged 17 to 19 (III and IV grades of high school), participated in the research. Of the total number of respondents, 595 (62%) were girls, and 363 (38%) were boys. The average age of the participants was 17.8 years.

Of the total number of respondents, 61% stated that they had sexual relations. About gender, statistically significantly more male respondents (65%) than female respondents (59%) entered

sexual relations.

When asked when they had sexual intercourse for the first time, the most significant number of surveyed students answered at the age of 17 - 35%, then at the age of 16 - 25%, and at the age of 18 - 18%.

The average age of all surveyed students when they had their first sexual relationship was 16.40 years. The average age of the male respondents was 15.80 years, while the average age of the female respondents was statistically significantly later, 16.77 years. Male respondents enter into sexual relations statistically significantly earlier than female respondents.

We also compared the average age at first sexual intercourse with success in school. A higher average age at first sexual intercourse is present in a greater number of cases with greater success in school (Table 1 and Graph 1). Among adolescents, there is no statistically significant difference in the average age at entering sexual relations for the first time according to success at the end of the last school year, while there are statistically significant differences among adolescent girls.

Table 1. Age at first sexual intercourse, by success

Sufficient	15,80
Good	15,89
Very good	16,42
Excellent	16,77

Graph 1. Age at first sexual intercourse, by success level

According to their assessment, the majority of respondents (90% - 88% of girls and 94% of boys) believe that they have all the necessary information about contraception. 96% of respon-

dents had heard of at least one method of contraception, while only 36% knew exactly which methods were reliable. The most frequently mentioned forms of protection were condoms (77%) and contraceptive pills (32%), while long-term methods such as IUDs or implants were rarely known (<2%).

Older respondents (IV grade of high school) showed statistically significantly better overall knowledge compared to younger respondents (III grade of high school). Girls showed statistically substantially greater understanding and a more responsible attitude towards their reproductive health compared to boys. Only 42% of respondents knew precisely when the fertile days in the menstrual cycle are, while only 35% of respondents answered questions about sexually transmitted infections correctly.

Contraceptives are used by 87% of those who have had sex, of which 91% of male and 85% of female respondents. 62% use some protection in every relationship. Condom, as a means of contraception, is the most frequently used contraceptive method, 77% of respondents. 1% of the respondents encountered the problem of unwanted pregnancy.

Only 42% of respondents visited a gynecologist, urologist, or youth counseling center. Statistically significant, a greater number of adolescent girls who have had sexual relations go to gynecological examinations.

In the majority of cases, respondents can turn to their parents in case of problems (86%). Regarding the conversation with their parents, 42% of respondents state that they have openly discussed sexuality with their parents at least once, while 58% have never done so.

Discussion

The results of this research indicate that the knowledge of adolescents about reproductive health is not at a satisfactory level, which mainly refers to the understanding of fundamental biological processes, contraceptive methods, and PPIs. It was observed that, although most adolescents have basic information, it is often based on incorrect or incomplete information

and can have serious consequences for the health of young people, as well as for their future reproductive decisions. These findings are consistent with previous studies conducted in the region and around the world, which indicate a lack of comprehensive sexuality education in educational systems [11, 12]. For example, research in Serbia and neighboring countries has shown that young people often acquire information from unreliable sources, such as the Internet and peers, which can contribute to the spread of wrong beliefs. This was also demonstrated in earlier research conducted in the region's countries, where authors highlighted the low awareness among adolescents of reproductive health and the need for systematic education [13, 14]. For example, research in secondary schools in Croatia showed that more than 60% of students were not entirely sure how the menstrual cycle works, and only 35% of respondents correctly identified the correct use of condoms [15]. These findings are consistent with our results, confirming the existence of a broader problem in access to reproductive health education.

Within our analysis, significant differences in knowledge levels were observed among different subgroups of respondents. Girls showed a higher level of knowledge compared to their male peers, especially in areas related to the menstrual cycle, contraception, and the importance of regular gynecological examinations. This is in line with the work of Kirby [16], who pointed out that girls generally show a higher level of interest in reproductive health information, often due to more immediate physiological experiences and greater social pressure to behave responsibly about sexual activities. Grammar school students had significantly better results than vocational school students, which may be a consequence of differences in curricula and a possible greater focus on general educational content in grammar schools. These results indicate the existence of educational inequality in access to key information on reproductive health.

Of particular concern is the fact that a significant percentage of respondents express conser-

vative attitudes towards the topics of sexuality, especially regarding open conversations with parents and health professionals. Respondents repeatedly stated that they felt shame, fear of judgment, or considered the topics "not appropriate for their age," which may indicate deep-rooted cultural taboos that make it challenging to create a safe and open environment for learning and discussion. Such attitudes can lead to avoidance of health examinations, non-use of contraception, and increased risk of unwanted pregnancies and sexually transmitted diseases [17, 18].

By WHO recommendations, comprehensive sexual education must be part of the school curriculum, starting with early adolescence. It must be adapted to the age, cultural context, and real needs of young people. Education must include topics such as physiological changes in puberty, menstruation, pregnancy, contraception, protection against sexually transmitted infections, emotional aspects of sexual relations, as well as the rights of young people to access information and health services [11, 12].

Limitations of our study include the fact that it is a cross-sectional study conducted in a limited geographic area, which may affect the overall representativeness of the data. Additionally, a questionnaire with a self-assessment component was used, which carries the risk of subjective bias and the potential for socially desirable answers. Additionally, the research did not include parents, teachers, or health workers, who play a crucial role in shaping the knowledge and attitudes of adolescents. For future research, it is recommended to incorporate qualitative methods to gain a deeper understanding of the reasons behind certain attitudes and behaviors [19].

Based on the findings, it is clear that there is a need for the systematic introduction of comprehensive sex education into the school curriculum, grounded in scientific evidence and tailored to each age group. Additionally, it is crucial to enhance the capacities of the school and health system to provide adolescents with easier access to counseling and reproductive health services.

Conclusion

The results of this research indicate the existence of significant gaps in adolescents' knowledge of reproductive health, as well as pronounced variations in attitudes that reflect the influence of education, social environment, and cultural norms. Of particular concern is that a large number of respondents demonstrate limited understanding of important aspects of sexual health, including contraception, prevention of sexually transmitted infections, and access to health services. Identified differences in knowledge and attitudes depending on demographic characteristics indicate the need for a more targeted approach in education. Girls and high school students showed a higher level of information, which suggests that certain groups of adolescents remain systematically neglected when it comes to access to adequate information about reproductive health.

These findings confirm the urgent need to introduce comprehensive, scientifically based, and age-appropriate sex education into the formal education system. In addition to school education, it is essential to involve parents, health-care workers, and the broader community to create a supportive environment that fosters the development of knowledge and healthy attitudes in young people. Further research should incorporate qualitative methods and a wider geographical distribution of respondents to gain a deeper understanding of the factors that shape adolescents' knowledge, behavior, and attitudes towards reproductive health. A systematic and integrated approach in education is a key step towards improving the health and well-being of young generations.

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